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**Measurement of Errors and Misconceptions:
Interviews and Open-ended Tests, Multiple-
Choice Tests, Two-tier Tests and Three-Tier Test**

Dr. Ritu Bala

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Dr. Ritu Bala⁵

Abstract

The diagnostic tests intend to discover specific deficiencies in learning. Although, diagnostic tests are very helpful in identifying the misconceptions of the students but their effectiveness is doubted as students do not justify their answers. To overcome this problem two-tier tests were used. However, the researchers also found that two-tier tests also overestimate the proportions of the misconceptions, as the students are not asked for their confidence about their answers. They regard all errors as misconceptions. Gap in knowledge cannot be discriminated by two-tier tests. So a third-tier is required to be sure that whether a wrong answer for the first two tiers is a misconception or a mistake due to lack of knowledge. In this paper, we shall compare variety of methods: Interviews and Open-ended Tests, Multiple-Choice Tests, Two-tier Tests and Three-Tier Test to identify students' misconceptions through the lens of review of literature. The three-tier test has the ability to assess errors committed by students and to differentiate misconceptions from false negatives and lack of knowledge as the sources of errors.

Keywords:

Measurement of Errors and Misconceptions, Interviews and Open-ended Tests, Multiple-Choice Tests, Two-tier Tests, Three-Tier Test, Errors and Misconceptions, Errors, Misconceptions, Measurement.

⁵ M.A. (Maths.), NET, Ph.D. (Education), PGDHE, e-mail: ritu_bala11@yahoo.com

Introduction:

The researches seem to show that the first step in diffusing errors and misconceptions is to detect them. When the misconception studies started to appear in the literature, science educators have focused on developing valid and reliable methods to identify them. Therefore, they proposed variety of methods to identify students' misconceptions such as various types of interviews, word associations, open-ended questions, multiple-choice tests, multiple-choice tests with explanation, and two-tiered multiple-choice tests (Al-Rubayea, 1996). In this paper, we shall compare variety of methods: Interviews and Open-ended Tests, Multiple-Choice Tests, Two-tier Tests and Three-Tier Test to identify students' misconceptions through the lens of review of literature.

Interviews and Open-ended Tests:

Osborne and Gilbert (1980) reported a technique to explore students' views of the world. The technique is a kind of interview; the interview-about-instances. In this kind of interview, the investigator presents some cards on which familiar situations are depicted for the interviewee. The cards may or may not include instances of a concept and the students are asked to think about if there is an instance of concept on the card, thereby eliciting the student conceptions. The researchers also presented advantages and limitations of the interview-about-instances.

Advantages can be listed as:

- It is applicable over a wide range of age
- It is enjoyable for interviewer and interviewee
- It has advantages over written answers in terms of flexibility and depth of the investigation

- Classifying instances is more pertinent and penetrating than asking for a definition
- It is concerned with the students' view rather than merely examining if the students have the correct scientific view.

And some limitations can be listed as:

- There is the problem of choosing a limited but adequate set of instances.
- The order of instances may influence student responses
- Interviews, transcriptions and analysis of transcripts are time consuming
- There are the difficulties associated with interviews and the analysis of the interview data, e.g. difficult to report succinctly.

Although, researchers gain more information by depth of probing and flexibility of questioning by interviews (Beichner, 1994), they require a large amount of time to interview with a large number of students (Chen et al., 2002) to get greater generalization (Beichner, 1994). Moreover, these methods also require additional training of researchers (Treagust and Haslam, as cited in Chen et al., 2002). Also, although open-ended questionnaires give students more time to think and write about their ideas, interpretation and analyzing the results of the open-ended questionnaires are difficult and time consuming (Al-Rubayea, 1996).

Multiple-Choice Tests:

Multiple-choice tests have been found an effective way of identifying the misconceptions of the students by researchers. Bar (as cited in Al-Rubayea, 1996) states that multiple-choice tests are more effective than oral or written open-ended essays in detecting students' misconceptions. Tamir (1990) suggests that when multiple-choice tests are used wisely, they are excellent to identify student

conceptions, including misconceptions despite of great amount of criticism. Some characteristics of multiple-choice tests are presented as follow:

- Multiple-choice tests permit coverage of a wide range of topics in a relatively short time.
- They can be used to measure different levels of learning.
- They are objective in terms of scoring and therefore more reliable.
- They are easily and quickly scored and lend themselves to machine scoring.
- They avoid unjustified penalties to students who know their subject matter but are poor writers.
- They are suitable for item analysis by which various attributes can be determined, such as which items on a test are too easy, which were too hard, which are ambiguous, etc. (Hedges, 1966; Wesman, 1971, as cited in Tamir, 1990).

Beichner (1994) suggested a model for developing and analyzing a diagnostic test in uncovering student difficulties. He initially mentions about interviews and multiple-choice tests. Interviews are very useful in probing the answers of students to the researcher's questions. However, they need too much time for conducting on large numbers of students and analyzing them. At that point, multiple-choice tests are very useful, because they can be easily administered to large numbers of students and analyzed, thus we can generalize our results. Beichner (1994) suggested the combination of interviews and multiple-choice tests.

It is beneficial to focus on the process of test development suggested by Beichner (1994):

1. Formulate a list of specific objectives after recognizing the need for the test.

2. Carry out a pilot study for the last version of the list of specific objectives. (Objectives which nearly all students succeed in must be removed, because the aim of the test is to uncover students' difficulties, not their achievement.)
3. Ask open-ended questions of a group of students to determine the most frequently appearing mistakes.
4. Write three items for each objective to produce the test by using the mistakes found in the open-ended questions as distracters. (Items may be selected from some outside sources, such as textbooks, question banks, etc.)
5. To modify several of the questions, administer the test to 100-150 students.
6. To establish the content validity, distribute the revised test to some educators and professors. Then, ask them to complete the tests, comment on the appropriateness of the objectives, criticize the items, and match items to objectives.
7. Administer the test to a sample whose size is enough.
8. Conduct an instructional activity to the sample of students.
9. Again administer the test to the sample after a little modification.
10. Calculate the Pearson product-moment correlation to examine if the two test versions are similar (parallel forms). Steps 7, 8, 9, 10 indicate equivalent-forms method.
11. Calculate a paired sample t-test to look for if the difference between mean scores of pre-and post-test is significant. A significantly increase in the mean scores is the evidence of validity.

Beichner (1994) administered the test to 524 students after constructing his valid and reliable test to uncover student difficulties. Analysis from this data revealed that the test was certainly useful for diagnostic purposes and should be helpful as a research tool.

Multiple-choice tests have many advantages. They can be scored immediately and objectively. Teacher can administer them easily and they are applicable to large number of students (Al-Rubayea, 1996). Moreover, multiple-choice tests were better liked by the students than other measures and could give diagnostic information. Scott (as cited in Marx, 1988) pointed out nine appropriate reasons for using of multiple-choice tests:

- They provide greater variety of questions.
- They can be qualitative questions regarding physics principles.
- Choosing between alternatives and having a general understanding are much more like real life.
- Options act like hints.
- The teachers can ask subtle points with them.
- Multiple-choice items are next best thing to essay type questions.
- The teachers can ask for a quick numerical calculation and make them worth a point.
- More material can be covered.
- They are good for review.

There are also some points of criticism of the multiple-choice tests. According to Rollnick and Mahooana (1999) the disadvantage of multiple-choice tests is that questions do not provide deep enough inside into the students' ideas on the topic and students very often give correct answers for wrong reasons. According to Stiggins (as cited in Cataloglu, 2002) multiple-choice tests direct the students' attention on information in isolation by testing one element at a time. Therefore, the larger context and structure of relationships between and among the elements get lost. According to Bork (as cited in Marx, 1988) multiple-choice tests should never be used. He expressed five reasons to support his assertion:

- Multiple choice items encourage guessing.
- The items are not from real life situations.
- They are not friendly for students because, students see them in somewhat a derogatory fashion, connected with the fact that guessing is involved.
- He stated that ‘There is no real use for them. For example, we hardly ever use multiple-choice in the computer based quizzes’.
- Writing good items is too difficult.

He had seen A-grade students did B-grade in the multiple choice exams and vice-versa. He attributed this to careless wording of stems and questions based on weak examples. Sandin (as cited in Marx, 1988) added two more reasons for why multiple-choice tests are not effective:

- Students may have extracted the right answer by a fortuitous combination of errors.
- Multiple-choice tests heavily depend on reading comprehension skills.

According to Al-Rubeyya (1996) when researchers used them to identify the students’ misconceptions, researchers became worried about memorization of the students to select the correct answer. As it is seen, multiple-choice tests are easily applicable and their results can be analyzed quickly and easily. The problem is their effectiveness. To overcome this problem (Al-Rubayea, 1996) recommended that students should justify their answers. As a result, researchers extended the multiple-choice tests into several tiers, two or three tiers.

Two-tier Tests:

Two-tier tests include, in addition to selecting correct answer among the distracters, multiple reasons or justifications from which the students choose their reason for their response. Treagust (as cited in Odom and Barrow, 1995) described

the item format of the two-tier multiple choice tests as the first tier consisting of a content question with two, three, or four choices. The second-tier consists of four possible reasons for the first part with three of them alternative reasons and one desired reason. The second-tier can also include a blank that students can write a reason for the first tier when they can not see their reasons among the alternatives of the second-tier (Griffard and Wandersee, 2001).

Development process of two-tier tests

Developing reliable and valid conceptual diagnostic tests is a struggling process and requires great efforts (Zeilik, 1997). The development process of a two-tier test was defined by Treagust in three main phases (as cited in Odom and Barrow, 1995):

Phase 1:

1. The content boundaries were defined with a list of propositional knowledge statements.
2. Content validity of propositional knowledge statements was determined.

Phase 2:

3. Students' misconceptions were identified by interviews.
4. Multiple-choice questions with free response reasons were constructed and administered.

Phase 3:

5. Final test questions were constructed based on multiple-choice questions with free response reasons.
6. The final test questions were revised and a pilot study was conducted.
7. Final content and face validity of each test item were determined with the assistance of a specification grid.

8. The final version of the test was administered.

Some two-tier diagnostic tests (Tan et al. 2002) were developed based on this process in different fields of science education. Most of the development of two-tier diagnostic tests includes both interviews and open-ended questionnaires or multiple-choice tests to identify the misconceptions of the students which will be used for distracters of the two-tier test. Including interview method gives a chance to researcher to probe the students' mind deeper and ask the questions with more flexibility. On the other hand, including open-ended or multiple-choice tests gives a chance to the researcher to deal with more subjects to generalize the results (Beichner, 1994).

Tsai and Chou (2002) stated that 'since, two-tier test is in multiple-choice format, it is much easier for teachers to score or interpret students' responses. In this way, even with numerous students, a teacher can efficiently diagnose their alternative conceptions.' According to Zeilik (1997) teachers can use these diagnostic tests for formative and summative assessments over semesters. If teachers use them as a formative test, they will understand their students' cognitive states, preconceptions and misconceptions prior to instruction. Therefore, they can take some precautions for misconceptions which can possibly obstruct the lecture. For example, they can tutor the students in their weak areas individually or assign the students into heterogeneous cooperative learning teams. If teachers use the diagnostic tests for summative assessment, they will see positive or negative impact of their instruction method which can serve feedback for later on instructions. However, it is important to say that results of the diagnostic tests cannot be used for assigning the grades of the students. Because, the main purpose of the tests is to diagnose not to assess achievement of the students. However, it is important to say that results of the diagnostic tests cannot be used for assigning the grades of the

students. Because, the main purpose of the tests is to diagnose not to assess achievement of the students.

Criticism of the two-tier tests:

Although, diagnostic tests are very helpful for teachers to identify the misconceptions of the students, some researchers criticize them. According to Yaroch (as cited in Griffard and Wandersee, 2001), forced choice instruments like two-tier tests give clues to the students to select correct answers that they would not have had in interviews and open-ended questions. Griffard and Wandersee (2001) investigated the effectiveness of a two-tier instrument developed by Haslam and Treagust in 1987 about photosynthesis. The test was given to the students and wanted them to think aloud while they were answering the items. They found that, using unnecessarily wording to distract students caused them to make mistakes. It is not certain that whether these mistakes were due to misconceptions that students had or unnecessarily wording of the test. Moreover, these unnecessarily wording can cause to create a new misconception in students' mind. They also stated that 'students considered the second-tier as a distinct multiple-choice item and finalized their choice on the basis of whether it logically followed from their response to the first tier. Therefore, two-tier test seemed to measure the students' test-taking skills rather than the extant knowledge'. Moreover, the feelings of the students are very important. Students take these types of tests with different amounts of sincerity, anxiety, persistence and meticulousness that can confound the test results. They also criticized the two tier test about the estimating the proportions of the misconceptions. According to them, two-tier tests overestimate the proportions of the misconceptions because gap in knowledge cannot be discriminated by two-tier tests. Therefore a third-tier is necessary to be sure that whether a wrong answer for the first two-tier is a misconception or a mistake due to lack of knowledge.

Three-tier Tests:

Three-tier tests are very similar to the two-tier tests. In three-tier tests, an item has one additional tier which asks students confidence about the answer of the former two-tiers (Cataloglu, 2002). Pesman 2005; Turker 2005 and Ozlem 2007 developed three-tier test to assess the misconceptions of the high school students. Eryilmaz and Surmeli (2002) developed a three-tier test to assess the misconceptions of the high school students about heat and temperature. According to them, all misconceptions are errors, but not all errors are misconceptions. Some errors may stem from lack of knowledge. If a student explains his/her error as a true with reasons and says his/her confidence, it is acceptable that this student has misconception. In two-tier tests and multiple-choice tests, the students are not asked about their confidence about their answers. They regard all errors as misconceptions. So three-tier tests are required to remove this problem. These types of tests have one more tier in which the students are asked about their confidence about the first two tiers. The first tier is a normal multiple choice test, the second-tier is again a multiple choice test with one correct reason and some alternative reasons, and the third-tier asks the student if he/she is sure for the responses in the first two tiers. If a student gives the desired responses for the first two tiers and chooses “Yes, I am sure” for the last tier, then the response is regarded as the correct answer. In their study, they compared the proportions of the misconceptions that the students had with respect to the tiers of the items. They found the students had misconceptions with an average 46% for the first tiers of the items, with an average 27% for the first two-tier of the items and with an average 18% for all three tiers of the items. From these results the researchers concluded that one tier and two-tier tests overestimated the proportions of the misconceptions. For the one-tier tests, it is accepted all wrong answers are misconceptions. However, some of

the wrong answers may be false negatives which are incorrect answers by mistake in spite of correct reasons in the second-tier and some may be due to randomly given answers by chance because related reasons of the incorrect answers were not chosen on the second tiers. Therefore, 19% (subtracting 27% from 46%) indicated incorrect answers by mistake or chance. The researchers also found that two tiers tests also overestimated the proportions of the misconceptions. Because as mentioned above, it is required if a student has a misconception he/she should say his/her confidence. In two-tier tests the students are not asked whether they are confident about for their responses. The researchers found that 9% of the students were not confident for the answers of the first two-tiers even if their answers indicated the misconceptions. They explained that those students gave incorrect answers due to lack of knowledge. To sum up, the researchers concluded that three-tier tests assess the misconceptions of the students more validly than one-tier and two tier tests. The scoring pattern in these tests was as under:

1. **Only First Tier Score:** It was obtained by using each student's choice selections indicating misconceptions and student answers for only the first tier of items on the test. Total misconceptions assessed by each student and also the percentage of misconceptions assessed for each item according to only the first tiers were calculated.
2. **Only First Two Tier Score:** It was obtained by using each student's choice selections indicating misconceptions and student answers for only the first two tiers of items on the test. Total misconceptions assessed by each student and also the percentage of misconceptions assessed for each item according to only the first two tiers were calculated.
3. **All the Three Tier Score:** It was obtained by using each student's choice selections indicating misconceptions and student answers for all three tiers of

items on the test. Total misconceptions assessed by each student and also the percentage of misconceptions assessed for each item according to the all three tiers were calculated.

- 4. Only Third Tier Score:** It was obtained by using each student's answers for only the third tier of items on test. Total scores for each student namely confidence scores of each student was calculated and also the percentage of confidence according to only third tier for each item were calculated.

In this type of the test, the percentage of misconceptions decreases as the tier of the test increases. The difference (decrease) in the percentage of the misconceptions in one tier and two-tier test gives false negatives (the wrong answers given by students who give right reasons) and the difference (decrease) in the percentage of the misconceptions in two tier- test and three-tier test attributes to lack of knowledge because the misconceptions cannot be accepted unless the student shows his confidence in the third tier. Therefore, it can be stated that after the identification of errors and prior to the identification of misconceptions: false negatives and lack of knowledge may emerge in between.

Conclusion:

The diagnostic tests intend to discover specific deficiencies in learning. Although, diagnostic tests are very helpful in identifying the misconceptions of the students but their effectiveness is doubted as students do not justify their answers. To overcome this problem two-tier tests were used (Odom et al., 1995; Cataloglu, 2002 and Tan et al. 2002). The researchers also found that two-tier tests also overestimate the proportions of the misconceptions. In two-tier tests, the students are not asked for their confidence about their answers. They regard all errors as misconceptions. Gap in knowledge cannot be discriminated by two-tier tests. So a

third-tier is required that asks the students to show their confidence about the answers given in the first two tiers. Third-tier is necessary to be sure that whether a wrong answer for the first two tiers is a misconception or a mistake due to lack of knowledge (Eryilmaz and Surmeli 2002; Pesman 2005; Turker 2005 and Ozlem 2007). The three-tier test has the ability to assess students' performance in the subject, errors committed by students in the test (wrong answers in the first tier) and to differentiate misconceptions from false negatives and lack of knowledge as the sources of errors.

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